

1. Appendixes

Appendix A. Determination of derivatives of kinetic and potential energy functions

From expressions (9) and (11), it can be seen that the position of the load on a flexible suspension depends on four generalized coordinates: α , x , z and u . The vertical component of the load velocity from the deviations of its flexible suspension from the vertical is neglected when determining the kinetic energy of the load, as it is an order of magnitude smaller than its total vertical velocity component. In this regard, the following dependence of the vertical component of the load velocity is used

$$\dot{y} = \dot{\alpha}(L + z \cos \alpha) + \dot{z} \sin \alpha - \dot{u}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

Partial derivatives of kinetic energy (7) with respect to generalized coordinates of the arrow system are found taking into account expression (A1):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \alpha} &= -[J_1 + J_2 + m_2(z + L)(z + L - l)]\omega^2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + m\dot{y} \frac{\partial \dot{y}}{\partial \alpha}; \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial \beta} &= 0; \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial u} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = m\dot{x}\omega^2; \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = m_2(z + L - l)(\dot{\alpha}^2 + \omega^2(\cos \alpha)^2) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2})$$

In addition, partial derivatives of kinetic energy (7) were found for generalized velocities, as a result of which the following was obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{\alpha}} &= [J_1 + J_2 + m_2(z + L)(z + L - l)]\dot{\alpha} + m\dot{y} \frac{\partial \dot{y}}{\partial \alpha}; \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{\beta}} &= J_3\dot{\beta}; \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{u}} = m\dot{y} \frac{\partial \dot{y}}{\partial u}; \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{x}} = m\dot{x}; \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{z}} = m_2\dot{z} + m\dot{y} \frac{\partial \dot{y}}{\partial z}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

As a result, the complete derivatives of expressions (A3) with respect to time are determined:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{\alpha}} &= [J_1 + J_2 + m_2(z + L)(z + L - l)]\ddot{\alpha} + 2m_2\dot{\alpha}\dot{z} \left(z + L - \frac{l}{2} \right) + m \left(\ddot{y} \frac{\partial \dot{y}}{\partial \alpha} + \dot{y} \frac{\partial \ddot{y}}{\partial \alpha} \right); \\ \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{\beta}} &= J_3\ddot{\beta}; \quad \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{u}} = m \left(\ddot{y} \frac{\partial \dot{y}}{\partial u} + \dot{y} \frac{\partial \ddot{y}}{\partial u} \right); \quad \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{x}} = m\ddot{x}; \quad \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{z}} = m_2\ddot{z} + m \left(\ddot{y} \frac{\partial \dot{y}}{\partial z} + \dot{y} \frac{\partial \ddot{y}}{\partial z} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A4})$$

Partial derivatives of potential energy (12) are also determined by generalized coordinates, which have the following form:

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \alpha} = \left[\frac{m_1 L}{2} + m_2 \left(z + L + \frac{l}{2} \right) + m(z + L) \right] g \cos \alpha + mgu \frac{\partial v}{\partial \alpha} \sin v; \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \beta} = cr[\beta r - z + z_0 - (u_0 - u)n]; \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial z} = -c[\beta r - z + z_0 + (u_0 - u)n] + (m_2 + m)g \sin \alpha + mgu \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \sin v; \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial u} = cn[\beta r - z + z_0 - (u_0 - u)n] - mg \left(\cos v - u \frac{\partial v}{\partial u} \sin v \right); \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial x} = mgu \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \sin v. \quad (\text{A9})$$

Partial derivatives of the angular coordinate of deviation from the vertical of the flexible suspension of the load (11) are used in expressions (A5),..., (A9), therefore, their values are determined:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial v}{\partial \alpha} &= \frac{L+z}{u} \sin \alpha; \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} = -\frac{\cos \alpha}{u}; \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial u} &= -\frac{v}{u}; \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{u}.\end{aligned}\tag{A10}$$

After substituting expressions (A10) into dependencies (A5), ..., (A9) and taking into account that for jib crane systems $v \leq 12^\circ$, it can be assumed that $\sin v \approx v$, $\cos v \approx 1$. As a result of taking into account the assumptions made, expressions for the partial derivatives of the potential energy of the arrow system in generalized coordinates were obtained:

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \alpha} = \left[\frac{m_1 L}{2} + m_2 \left(z + L - \frac{l}{2} \right) + m(z+L) \right] g \cos \alpha + mg(L+z)v \sin \alpha;\tag{A11}$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \beta} = cr[\beta r - z + z_0 - (u_0 - u)n];\tag{A12}$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial z} = -c[\beta r - z + z_0 - (u_0 - u)n] + [(m_2 + m)\sin \alpha - m v \cos \alpha]g;\tag{A13}$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial u} = cn[\beta r - z + z_0 - (u_0 - u)n] - mg(1 + v^2);\tag{A14}$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial x} = mg v;\tag{A15}$$

Taking into account the assumptions made above, the partial derivatives of the vertical coordinate of the center of mass of the load in the generalized coordinates of the system in expressions (A3) and (A4) have the following form:

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial \alpha} = (z+L)\cos \alpha; \quad \frac{\partial y}{\partial z} = \sin \alpha; \quad \frac{\partial y}{\partial u} = -1.$$

Appendix B. Penalty functions for ensuring constraints (27)..., (32)

$$\begin{aligned}
p_1 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } M_1 \geq M_{1\min}; \\ \frac{M_1}{M_{1\max}}, & \text{if } M_1 < M_{1\min}; \end{cases} & p_7 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } P_1 \geq P_{1\min}; \\ \frac{P_1}{P_{1\max}}, & \text{if } P_1 < P_{1\min}; \end{cases} \\
p_2 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } M_1 < M_{1\max}; \\ \frac{M_1}{M_{1\max}}, & \text{if } M_1 > M_{1\max}; \end{cases} & p_8 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } P_1 < P_{1\max}; \\ \frac{P_1}{P_{1\max}}, & \text{if } P_1 < P_{1\max}; \end{cases} \\
p_3 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } F_2 \geq F_{2\min}; \\ \frac{F_2}{F_{2\max}}, & \text{if } F_2 < F_{2\min}; \end{cases} & p_9 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } P_2 \geq P_{2\min}; \\ \frac{P_2}{P_{2\max}}, & \text{if } P_2 < P_{2\min}; \end{cases} \\
p_4 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } F_2 \leq F_{1\min}; \\ \frac{F_2}{F_{2\max}}, & \text{if } F_2 > F_{2\max}; \end{cases} & p_{10} &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } P_2 < P_{2\max}; \\ \frac{P_2}{P_{2\max}}, & \text{if } P_2 < P_{2\max}; \end{cases} \\
p_5 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } M_3 \geq M_{3\min}; \\ \frac{M_3}{M_{3\max}}, & \text{if } M_3 < M_{3\min}; \end{cases} & p_{11} &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } P_3 \geq P_{3\min}; \\ \frac{P_3}{P_{3\max}}, & \text{if } P_3 < P_{3\min}; \end{cases} \\
p_6 &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } M_3 < M_{3\max}; \\ \frac{M_3}{M_{3\max}}, & \text{if } M_3 < M_{3\max}; \end{cases} & p_{12} &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } P_3 < P_{3\max}; \\ \frac{P_3}{P_{3\max}}, & \text{if } P_3 < P_{3\max}. \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{B1}$$

Appendix C. Boundary conditions

Boundary conditions (25) and (26) are reduced to generalised coordinates of jib extension z , flexible jib suspension length u and change in its outreach x , as well as their time derivatives. The boundary conditions coordinates of the jib rotation α and the drive drum of the load hoisting mechanism β are expressed for this purpose through the above-mentioned generalised coordinates.

The initial conditions of motion are considered when $t=0$. The equation was obtained after substituting the initial boundary conditions (25) into dependencies (13) and (14), from which it was established that

$$\ddot{x} = \ddot{x}(0) = 0; \quad \ddot{\alpha} = \ddot{\alpha}(0) = 0. \tag{C1}$$

After substituting the initial conditions of motion (25) into equations (16) and (17), we obtain that

$$\ddot{u}_0 = \ddot{u}(0) = 0; \quad \ddot{u}_0 = \ddot{u}(0) = 0. \tag{C2}$$

The final conditions of motion are also considered, when $t=t_1$. After substituting the final conditions (26) into equations (13) and (14), we obtain that

$$\ddot{x}_1 = \ddot{x}(t_1) = 0; \tag{C3}$$

$$\ddot{\alpha}_1 = \ddot{\alpha}(t_1) = 0. \tag{C4}$$

As a result of substituting the final conditions of motion (26) into equations (16) and (17), we find:

$$\ddot{u}_1 = \ddot{u}(t_1) = 0; \tag{C5}$$

$$\ddot{u}_1 = \ddot{u}(t_1) = 0. \tag{C6}$$

Additional conditions regarding zero derivatives of the fourth-order coordinates of the jib section extension, changes in the length of the flexible load suspension and its projection at the beginning and end of movement

have been introduced. These boundary conditions ensure smoothness in the transitional mode of movement of the jib system links.

Appendix D. Determination of derivatives of functions $z(t)$ and $x(t)$

$$\dot{z}_1(t) = B_1 + 2B_2t + 3B_3t^2 + 4B_4t^3 + 5B_5t^4 + 6B_6t^5 + 7B_7t^6 + 8B_8t^7 + 9B_9t^8; \quad (D1)$$

$$\ddot{z}_1(t) = 2B_2 + 6B_3t + 12B_4t^2 + 20B_5t^3 + 30B_6t^4 + 42B_7t^5 + 56B_8t^6 + 72B_9t^7; \quad (D2)$$

$$\dddot{z}_1(t) = 6B_3 + 24B_4t + 60B_5t^2 + 120B_6t^3 + 210B_7t^4 + 336B_8t^5 + 504B_9t^6; \quad (D3)$$

$$z_1^{IV}(t) = 24B_4 + 120B_5t + 360B_6t^2 + 840B_7t^3 + 1680B_8t^4 + 3024B_9t^5; \quad (D4)$$

$$\dot{x}_1(t) = C_1 + 2C_2t + 3C_3t^2 + 4C_4t^3 + 5C_5t^4 + 6C_6t^5 + 7C_7t^6 + 8C_8t^7 + 9C_9t^8; \quad (D5)$$

$$\ddot{x}_1(t) = 2C_2 + 6C_3t + 12C_4t^2 + 20C_5t^3 + 30C_6t^4 + 42C_7t^5 + 56C_8t^6 + 72C_9t^7; \quad (D6)$$

$$\dddot{x}_1(t) = 6C_3 + 24C_4t + 60C_5t^2 + 120C_6t^3 + 210C_7t^4 + 336C_8t^5 + 504C_9t^6; \quad (D7)$$

$$x_1^{IV}(t) = 24C_4 + 120C_5t + 360C_6t^2 + 840C_7t^3 + 1680C_8t^4 + 3024C_9t^5; \quad (D8)$$

Appendix E. Determination of constants in functions $z(t)$ and $x(t)$

After substituting boundary conditions (34) and (35) into expressions (43), (D1), ..., (D4), it is obtained that:

$$B_0 = z_0, B_1 = B_2 = B_3 = B_4 = 0. \quad (E1)$$

The constants B_5, \dots, B_9 were found from the following system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} B_5 + B_6t_1 + B_7t_1^2 + B_8t_1^3 + B_9t_1^4 &= \frac{V_2}{2t_1^4}; \\ 10B_5 + 15B_6t_1 + 21B_7t_1^2 + 28B_8t_1^3 + 36B_9t_1^4 &= 0; \\ 10B_5 + 20B_6t_1 + 35B_7t_1^2 + 56B_8t_1^3 + 84B_9t_1^4 &= 0; \\ 5B_5 + 15B_6t_1 + 35B_7t_1^2 + 70B_8t_1^3 + 126B_9t_1^4 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (E2)$$

As a result of substituting boundary conditions (53) and (54) into expressions (63) and (72), ..., (75), it is obtained that:

$$C_0 = x_0, C_1 = C_2 = C_3 = C_4 = 0. \quad (E3)$$

The constants C_5, \dots, C_9 are found from the following system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} C_5 + C_6t_1 + C_7t_1^2 + C_8t_1^3 + C_9t_1^4 &= \frac{V_1}{2t_1^4}; \\ 5C_5 + 6C_6t_1 + 7C_7t_1^2 + 8C_8t_1^3 + 9C_9t_1^4 &= \frac{V_2}{t_1^4}; \\ 10C_5 + 15C_6t_1 + 21C_7t_1^2 + 28C_8t_1^3 + 36C_9t_1^4 &= 0; \\ 10C_5 + 20C_6t_1 + 35C_7t_1^2 + 56C_8t_1^3 + 84C_9t_1^4 &= 0; \\ 5C_5 + 15C_6t_1 + 35C_7t_1^2 + 70C_8t_1^3 + 126C_9t_1^4 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (E4)$$

Appendix F. Plot of criterion (54) as it is minimized.

To solve the problem, 15 independent runs of the algorithm were performed. For all runs, the penalty functions converged to zero at the final stage of the computation. The variance of the results (i.e., the values of the objective function obtained for different runs) was 0.017, which is approximately 2% of the best solution obtained. The best solution is presented in this paper.

Figure F1 shows the convergence graph of the generalized criterion (54) during the minimization procedure. In Fig. F1, the red line represents the value of criterion (54) obtained for the baseline solution of the optimization problem. After 12 iterations, solutions satisfying the prescribed constraints were obtained, and after a further 38 iterations, solutions providing the minimum value of the integral criterion (24) were found (the lower line with black dots). These solutions correspond to the optimal simultaneous start-up of the load-lifting and jib-lifting mechanisms, as well as the extension of the jib section, during steady crane slewing.

Fig F1. Plot of criterion convergence (54) when applying the VCT-PSO method